

A REFINED STUDY OF CRACK BRIDGING IN CONCRETE STRUCTURES

Mickael MULLER, Evelyne TOUSSAINT, Jean-François DESTREBECQ, Michel
GREDIAC

LERMES, Blaise Pascal University

24, avenue des Landais

63174 Aubière Cedex, France

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ABSTRACT

The use of composite materials is an attractive and promising solution to repair damaged concrete structures. This technique is rather recent since the first attempts were performed in the eighties. Some typical phenomena occur when concrete beams reinforced with composite materials are tested. For instance, the peeling off of the composite plate may lead to the sudden collapse of the repaired structure ([1] for instance), the number of cracks in the concrete increases or the opening of the initial cracks in the concrete decreases thanks to their bridging by the composite. The proper modeling of such phenomena remains however an open question. One of the main reasons is the lack of refined experimental results in the vicinity of the parts of the tested structures involved near the local singularities : the end of the composite plate and the area around the cracks bridged by the composite. The aim of the present work is to investigate the bridging of cracks in a reinforced concrete prism reinforced with composite plates. Some relevant theoretical or empirical models are available to describe and to predict the opening of the cracks in concrete structures. On the other hand and to the knowledge of the authors, similar results on concrete structures reinforced with composite plates are not available. In the same way, the state of stress/strain in the composite near the cracks in the concrete has not been investigated in the literature. Both experimental and numerical analyses were performed in the present study to provide more information on this important issue for concrete structures reinforced with composites.

First, refined measurements on concrete specimens repaired with SIKA Carbodur carbon/epoxy plates and subjected to tensile tests are carried out. A non-contact optical method based on image intercorrelation provides full-field measurement onto the surface of the tested specimens and allows the accurate measurement of the crack width. These experimental results are compared to the width of cracks in the unreinforced counterparts to emphasize the influence of the composite reinforcement.

Second, a model is proposed to predict the opening of cracks. It is based on the CEB-FIB Model Code [2] which is well established in the case of reinforced concrete. This model has been presently modified to account for the influence of the composite plates.

Both experimental and numerical results are presented and compared in the paper which is illustrated by typical displacement contours measured onto the surface of the tested specimens.

INTRODUCTION

Civil concrete structures are generally designed to sustain service life ranging between 50 and 100 years. The longevity depends on constitution and using of structures. Several parameters may reduce this lifespan like new service conditions, creep, environmental or fatigue effects [3][4] for instance.

Some economical reasons do not always allow the destruction and the construction of a new structure to replace a damaged one. In order to fulfill new service conditions and/or to reduce time effects, a solution consists in adding externally bonded composite plates. Designing both additional composite material and joint with concrete are critical points because reinforcements carry a part of the loading of the structure in order to relieve it. Moreover, particular phenomena occur in such structures like the sudden peeling-off of the reinforcement or the crack bridging by the composite. The aim here is to study this last particular point. Tensile tests are first carried out on reinforced concrete specimens in order to measure accurately the crack opening with a non-contact measurement technique. The specimens are then repaired and tested once again. Crack opening is measured and the influence of the composite is quantified. Both a numerical and a theoretical models are then developed and compared with the experimental results

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Tensile tests were performed even though bending tests are often described in the literature. The reason is that the state of stress is expected to be more homogeneous during tensile tests, allowing a better analysis of the cracking activity. The specimens consist of concrete prisms ($80 \times 80 \times 500 \text{ mm}^3$) reinforced with four re-bars parallel to their longitudinal axis. Concrete was prepared with the following material proportions : free water/cement = 0.59 and cement/sand/coarse aggregate/fine aggregate = 1.2/2.15/2.46/0.24.

Because of the dimensions of the specimens, the coarse aggregate was of 8 mm maximum size. The compressive strength of the concrete was about 35 MPa at 28 days. The specimens were demoulded after 24 hours. Then they were cured until testing day by keeping them in a plastic foil. Composite plates were bonded onto two opposite faces of some of the concrete prisms. They were cut from Sika Carbodur S 812 carbon/epoxy plates. They contained 68% volumetric fraction of high strength fibres and 32 % of epoxy resin. The plates were 80 mm wide, 340 mm long and 1.35 mm thick. The longitudinal Young's modulus of the composite was 165 GPa and its tensile strength was 2800 MPa. The surfaces to be bonded were prepared as suggested by the composite supplier. The surface of the concrete was brushed to remove laitance, grease and other dirt. The composite plates were cleaned and grease was removed with Sikadur cleaner. Then, the plates were symmetrically bonded onto the concrete with a two-part cold-curing epoxy resin adhesive (see Figure 1). The resin and the hardener were mixed with a ratio in mass resin/hardener equal to 3/1. The adhesive was applied to both components to ensure there was sufficient excess to avoid a starved joint and to prevent the formation of air bubbles by the spread of adhesive from one surface to the other. A suitable device was used to achieve the desired thickness of 1 mm [5].

Displacement fields onto the concrete were measured with a non-contact procedure based on image intercorrelation. Pictures of the concrete surface were captured before and

after testing by a Philips camera which CCD grids exhibited 1024×1024 pixels. Both images were compared with a suitable programme “KISDEF” developed by Vacher [6] and displacement fields were deduced. Cracks caused discontinuities in this x-displacement field and their magnitude was their width. This method was very useful because the location of cracks remained unknown before testing. This did not allow the use of LVDT sensors for instance to measure crack opening. On the other hand, full-field measurements allow the detection of any crack within the measured field, provided that the width is greater than about 10 micrometers.

Fig. 1. Schematic view of the specimen.

REINFORCED CONCRETE SPECIMENS

Experimental results

Tensile tests were first performed on reinforced concrete specimens. Typical results are presented in this section. A typical x-displacement field is shown in Figure 2. Two drops in the field due to cracks are clearly visible. The two cracks here are located near the top end of the specimen. The width w of the second crack was measured at the center of the face every 5 kN. It is plotted vs. loading F in Figure 3. During the first cycle of loading, the crack appeared at $F=20$ kN. This value is consistent with the expected behaviour of the specimen (see model presented below). At unloading, the crack width decreased at a linear rate. A residual opening of the crack of about 24 micrometers was observed after unloading. As a matter of fact, the opening of cracks is resulting from a slip between the concrete and the Re-bars. Hence, the residual opening corresponds to a partially unrecoverable slip between the two materials. The hysteresis observed during the second loading cycle may be related to this mechanism. At the beginning of the second cycle, the crack width does not increase. In fact, the crack begins to open again between 5 and 10 kN. At unloading, the crack width is very similar for the two cycles. Three more loading cycles have been applied to the specimen. Only crack widths measured at $F=40$ kN for these three additional cracks are reported in Figure 3. They are very similar to values obtained at the same loading level during the two first cycles.

Fig. 2. Typical x-displacement field measured onto the reinforced concrete specimen at $F=40\text{kN}$

Fig. 3. Crack width w at the center of the reinforced specimen vs. F

The method has been used to study the crack spacing and crack width distribution as well. Five cracks were observed in the zone under investigation. By using the procedure described above, it was possible to determine the location and the width of each crack. The distance between neighbour cracks was found to be randomly distributed between 60 mm and 90 mm with an average spacing equal to 71.4 mm. The five cracks exhibit similar width w vs. loading F curves.

Modelling the crack opening

The width of cracks can be estimated using the CEB-FIB Model Code [4]. An average value w_m for crack width in the tensile zone of a reinforced concrete member is given by the following equation

$$w_m = \xi \varepsilon_{s2} \Delta l_m \quad (1)$$

where Δl_m is the average crack spacing, ε_{s2} is the strain in the tensile reinforcement in a cracked cross-section and ξ is a coefficient defined by

$$\xi = 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{sr}}{\sigma_s} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where σ_s and σ_{sr} are tensile stresses in the re-bars calculated in a cracked cross-section for the actual value of the loading and for the load that caused the cracking of the cross-section respectively. ε_{s2} is defined by the following equation

$$\varepsilon_{s2} = \frac{F}{E_s A_s} \quad (3)$$

where F is the loading applied to the specimen, E_s is the Young's modulus of the steel and A_s is the total cross-section area of the steel bars. Based on these equations, the evolution *vs.* loading F of the width of the crack located at mid-length of the tested specimen is estimated. The mean distance to neighbor cracks was measured during the test. It is equal to 80 mm. The value of the loading that has caused the cracking of the specimen, *ie.* $F= 18.9$ kN, is estimated on a basis of the tensile stress in the uncracked cross-section equal to the tensile strength of the concrete, *ie.* 2.7 MPa. The comparison between predicted and experimental crack width is shown in Figure 4. As may be seen, values predicted by the present model are in fair agreement with experimental ones.

The specimen has been modelled with a finite element programme and results are also reported in Figure 4. These numerical results are also in good agreement with measurements and values provided by the analytical model.

Fig. 4. Crack opening. Comparison between theory, experiments and FE simulations

SPECIMENS REPAIRED WITH COMPOSITE PLATES

Experimental results

The aim here is to analyze the influence of composite reinforcements on the crack behavior of repaired specimens. The specimens used in the previous part of the study were strengthened with pairs of composite plates bonded onto two opposite faces (see Figure 1). The pre-cracked specimens were unloaded during the application of the composite plates. Preparation of the concrete surface, bonding procedure and control of the adhesive joint thickness were processed as explained above. The length of the composite plates was designed in such a way that the two cracks closest to specimen ends were not bridged by the composite. All intermediate cracks were bridged.

The camera was adjusted in order to monitor the behaviour of the two first cracks at one end of the specimens. The load increased at a constant rate of displacement of the grip until the peeling-off of the concrete cover occurred in the zone of anchorage of one composite plate. Then, the load was decreased until complete unloading of the specimen.

The x-displacement measured by means of the non-contact method is presented in Figure 5 at $F=35$ kN, just before peeling-off. Two cracks are visible in this figure. The wider one (*ie.* the higher step in the longitudinal displacement) is the one closest to the specimen end. As explained above, this crack was not bridged by the composite. The next crack is located in the repaired zone of the specimen. Its width is less than the previous one (28 micrometers about, instead of 100 micrometers for the unbridged crack). This difference could be observed during the test since the first crack was visible by naked eye whereas the other one was not.

The evolution of the widths of the two cracks *vs.* loading F is plotted in Figure 6. Δw represents the increase in width of the cracks starting from the initial width (*ie.* residual width in the unloaded specimen) since this initial width cannot be measured by means of the optical method. Figure 6 clearly shows that the two investigated cracks behave in different ways. The behavior of the unbridged one is very similar to that of cracks in the unstrengthened specimen. The crack does not re-open before the load reaches 5 kN. Then the crack width increases in a pretty linear manner with the intensity of the load. Similarly, the bridged crack starts to open for $F \geq 5$ kN. Then its width increases at a much lower rate than the former one. Over 35kN, the width of the bridged crack increases suddenly at a much higher rate. This is due to the peeling-off of the concrete. As a matter of fact, the tensile force supported by the composite reinforcement is transferred to the concrete through the adhesive joint [1]. This mechanism yields a complex stress concentration in the concrete beneath composite end. If the concrete strength is exceeded, a crack forms and suddenly propagates within the concrete cover between reinforcing bars and composite plates, thus leading to brittle failure by peeling-off.

Fig. 5. x -displacement field on the surface of the repaired specimen at $F=35\text{kN}$

Fig. 6. Reinforced specimen. Increase in crack width Δw vs. loading F.

Modelling

Based on experimental evidences discussed in the previous section, it is possible to propose a modified expression for the analyzis of crack width in strengthened Reinforced Concrete specimens. Let N_p and N_s denote the tensile efforts supported by the composite plates and the steel bars respectively in a cracked section. Thus

$$N_s = F - N_p \quad (4)$$

Let us assume that the longitudinal strain in the composite may be expressed as $\beta\varepsilon_s$, where ε_s is the actual longitudinal strain in the re-bars and β is a coefficient which allows for the strain distribution between steel bars and composite plates. It is a trivial matter to deduce from the equilibrium of a cracked cross-section that

$$\varepsilon_s = \gamma \frac{F}{E_s A_s} \quad (5)$$

where γ is a reduction factor defined as follows

$$\gamma = \left(1 + \beta \frac{E_p A_p}{E_s A_s} \right)^{-1} < 1 \quad (6)$$

where E_p and A_p denote respectively the longitudinal modulus of elasticity and the cross-sectional area of the composite plates. Assuming that crack width may be estimated by Equation (2) on the basis of a reduced steel strain (Equation (5)), it yields

$$w_m = \gamma \xi \varepsilon_{s2} \Delta l_m \quad (7)$$

where ε_{s2} is given by Equation (3). Taking the material properties into account, the actual value of γ is 0.388 in the present work. Coefficient β is presently taken as 1 for the sake of simplicity. Crack widths calculated by the analytical method and by the FE model are compared with experimental results in Figure 7. Experimental and predicted values are comparable. By fitting FEM results and analytical values, it is possible to determine the β coefficient : $\beta \approx 0.90$ instead of the assumed value $\beta = 1$.

Fig. 7. Comparison between analytical, experimental and FEM simulated widths for a bridged crack

CONCLUSION

Reinforced concrete specimens have been subjected to tensile tests. After cracking, specimens have been reinforced with composite plates bonded onto two opposite faces. Displacement fields onto the concrete and the composite external surfaces have been measured by means of an optical method. An analytical model has been proposed on the base of CEB-FIB Model Code to predict crack opening in repaired specimens. Numerical simulations of cracked specimens (strengthened or un-strengthened) have been carried out. It has been shown that values predicted by CEB-FIB Model Code are consistent with 3D FEM simulations and with crack width measured by means of the optical method used. A crack bridging effect is observed in strengthened specimens. Indeed, measured widths are much

smaller for bridged cracks than for un-bridged ones. A predictive model based on CEB-FIB Model Code is proposed for crack width in strengthened reinforced concrete specimens. Compared with test results, this model proves conservative.

REFERENCES

1. Sierra-Ruiz V., Destrebecq J F, Grédiac M., The transfer length in concrete structures repaired with composite materials : a survey of some analytical models and simplified approaches, *Composite Structures*, **55**, pp. 445-454, 2002
2. CEB-FIB Model Code, Chap 7.4 Limit state of cracking, pp. 7.5-7.21, 1990
3. Barnes R. A. and Mays G. C., Fatigue performance of concrete beams strengthened with CFRP plates, *Journal of Composites for Construction*, **3**(2), pp. 63-72, 1999
4. Chajes M. J., Thomson T. A. and Farschman C. A., Durability of concrete beams externally reinforced with composite fabrics, *Construction and building materials*, **9**(3), pp. 141-148, 1995
5. Sierra-Ruiz V., Renforcement d'éléments structuraux en béton armé à l'aide de matériaux composites : analyse fine de la zone d'ancrage. Ph. D. Thesis, Blaise Pascal University, Clermont-Ferrand, France, 2002
6. Vacher P., Dumoulin S., Morestin F. and MGuil-Touchal S., Bidimensional strain measurement using digital images, *Proc. Instn. Mech. Engrs*, **213**, pp. 811-817, 1999